

X-Ray Diffraction Studies on 3-Methoxysalicylidene- α -(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)acetocarbohydrazone

K. R. CHOUKIMATH^a, R. T. PATTAR^a, V. G. TULASIGERI^{a*} and B. R. HAVINALE^b

^aDepartment of Physics, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003

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The ligand 3-methoxysalicylidene- α -(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)acetocarbohydrazone has been tested for its antibacterial and antifungal activities. The same has been exposed to the X-ray diffractometry studies for both the structural characterization and the accountability of strain broadening effects. The structure of the sample has emerged as tetragonal non-primitive system.

In recent years hydrazones (ligands) and its complexes have received the special attention for their medical and biological applicabilities. Such ligands have shown promising antibacterial and antifungal activities¹. Hence one such ligand 3-methoxysalicylidene- α -(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)acetocarbohydrazone has been undertaken in the present investigation for the detailed study of structural properties.

For the structural characterization, various techniques are used², and among them X-ray diffractometry (XRD) is nondestructive, noncontact, fast and sensitive. For the evaluation of various parameters and thereby deciding the structure of sample, XRD technique has been applied for the present ligand.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray data of the present ligand are given in Table 1. Its molecular formula as suggested by the elemental analysis is C₁₇H₁₇N₃O₄. There are twenty reflections (2θ) between 10° and 77° with maximum at $2\theta = 44.350^\circ$ as against $d = 2.041$ Å.

The X-ray pattern was indexed using software by trial and error method. Keeping in mind the characteristics of various symmetry systems this process was carried out till a good fit was obtained between the observed and calculated d and Q . Assuming tentatively structure to be tetragonal, the lattice parameter [a, b, c] of unit cell and cell volume were calculated. These were further refined by weight fraction method. Such refined parameters were used for finding out the space group and Laue group. All such calculated parameters are given in Table 1. In conjunction with such cell parameters, the conditions³ such as $a = b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, required for the sample to be tetragonal were tested and found to be satisfied. Hence, it may be concluded that the structure of the sample is tetragonal. Further to emphasize the above findings XRD data were fed to the software which could reproduce the structure to be tetragonal non-primitive system.

TABLE I—POWDER X-RAY DATA OF 3-METHOXYSALICYLIDENE- α -(*N*-PHENYLCARBAMOYL)ACETOCARBOHYDRAZONE

Peak no.	2θ	d_{obs}	d_{cal}	Q_{obs} 10^2	Q_{cal} 10^2	hkl	I/I_{max}	δQ 10^4
1	10.365	8.528	8.513	1.38	1.38	112	3.01	1.00
2	13.240	6.682	6.682	2.24	2.24	202,211	54.72	2.00
3	14.470	6.116	6.120	2.67	2.67	212	18.03	2.00
4	15.865	5.582	5.547	3.21	3.25	005	69.83	2.00
5	16.375	5.409	5.392	3.42	3.44	220	14.36	2.00
6	17.670	5.015	5.025	3.98	3.96	222,301	18.82	2.00
7	18.385	4.822	4.822	4.30	4.30	310	26.62	2.00
8	22.100	4.019	4.046	6.19	6.11	322	33.10	3.00
9	24.060	3.696	3.699	7.32	7.31	410,402	45.06	3.00
10	25.345	3.411	3.509	8.11	8.12	226,207	56.76	3.00
11	25.870	3.441	3.434	8.44	8.48	413	69.83	3.00
12	26.500	3.361	3.363	8.85	8.84	325,333	66.06	3.00
13	27.180	3.278	3.263	9.31	9.39	414	66.00	3.00
14	27.930	3.192	3.191	9.82	9.82	334	40.87	4.00
15	29.050	3.071	3.077	10.60	10.56	415,424	13.68	4.00
16	38.150	2.357	2.358	18.00	17.99	614	28.54	5.00
17	41.790	2.159	2.160	21.44	21.43	634	6.08	5.00
18	44.350	2.041	2.041	24.01	24.00	547,636	100	7.00
19	64.695	1.439	1.439	48.25	48.26	9110	27.57	7.00
20	77.930	1.225	1.225	59.63	59.67	597	18.82	7.00

Calculated cell parameters for tetragonal structure :

$a = 15.2489$ Å

$c = 27.7319$ Å

$a = b \neq c$

$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$

Space group = 14/mmm

Laue group = 4/m

Volume of unit cell = 6448.469 Å³

The experimental density was determined by the standard specific gravity method. Using this density and the values of molecular weights and volume of unit cell, the number of atoms per unit cell was approximated to 4. With this number, theoretical density was calculated. The other parameters such as packing fraction, pore fraction, particle size, radius of atom were also calculated. Space group and point group of the ligand were noted from the International Table for X-ray crystallography⁴. All these values are entered in Table 2.

TABLE 2—X-RAY PARAMETERS OF 3-METHOXSALICYLIDENE- α -(*N*-PHENYLCARBAMOYL)ACETOCARBOHYDRAZONE

Structure	: Tetragonal
Space group	: 14/mmm
Laue group	: 4/m
Point group	: 4/mmm
Symmetry of lattice	: Non-primitive
Lattice parameters	: $a=b=15.2489 \text{ \AA}$ $c=27.7319 \text{ \AA}$
Bond angles	: $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$
Vol. of unit cell	: 6448.469 \AA^3
Radius of atom	: 6.603 \AA
Vol. of atom	: 1205.90 \AA^3
Packing fraction	: 18.70%
Density of substance	
(Ther.)	: 0.3811 g/ml
(Expt.)	: 0.3805 g/ml
Pore fraction	: 0.29%
Thickness of particle	: 591 \text{ \AA}

Fig. 1. Analysis of inhomogeneity of 3-methoxysalicylidene- α -(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)acetocarbohydrazone.

The particle size of ligand was determined in the usual way. As this parameter makes possible the distinguishability between the natural particle size and the strain broadening effect hence it was sought to the analysis of

XRD pattern in greater detail⁵. This was done with different peaks by calculating fullwidth at half-maximum (B) corresponding to its Bragg θ 's and thereby computing Cos and Sin values. The nature of behaviour of these values is shown graphically in Fig. 1. The non-zero slope clearly indicates the presence of strain caused by inhomogeneous lattice distortion/or compositional fluctuations. This trend may be attributed to inhomogeneous properties of the natural particle. Hence, it may be said that the estimated particle size (591 \text{ \AA}) may not be that meaningful and realistic.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of reagent grade (E. Merck/B.D.H.). The ligand was prepared following the reported method⁶, and was purified by repetitive crystallization with ethanol. The purity of the product was checked by elemental analysis and physicochemical techniques.

The XRD spectra were recorded in the range $10-80^\circ$ on a Phillips PW-1710 diffractometer attached to digitized computer along with graphical assembly in which $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation source connected with the tube of Cu-NF 2 kV/20 mA was used.

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